

NUMERICAL SOLUTION FOR LINEAR PROGRAMMING PROBLEM WITH A FUZZY OBJECTIVE FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with a fuzzy linear programming problem where the fuzzy coefficient involves only in the objective function. The procedure starts with the construction of the penalty function in such a way that the equilibrium point converges to the solution of the fuzzy linear programming problem. The use of the fuzzy norm which was introduced and dealt in Effati is manipulated. The efficiency and importance of the method are shown with the compromise example of a fuzzy shortest path problem.

Keywords: Fuzzy trapezoidal number, Fuzzy energy function, Fuzzy differential Equations, Fuzzy neural network

1. INTRODUCTION

In the field of decision making, the concept of fuzzy sets are related to optimization when bellman and Zadeh [2] experimented in their work, followed by them, many other researchers showed their significant interest to develop the optimization in a fuzzy sense using fuzzy numbers in objective or conditions or both. Especially, Zimmerman [3] experimented with the fuzzy approach for solving multi-objective linear programming problems. Fuzzy linear programming problems with fuzzy constraints based on inequality are illustrated by Tanaka and Asai [4]. Ganesan and Veeramani [5] introduced a novel approach for solving linear optimization problems that have symmetric trapezoidal fuzzy numbers without converting them to the crisp linear programming problems. Also, many authors (Ebrahimnejad et al., [6]; Kumar et al., [7]; Jayalakshmi and Pandian [8]; Pandian [9]) introduced various approaches to solving fuzzy mathematical programming problems.

Solving the linear programming problems using penalty functions and Lagrange multipliers with the knowledge of neural networks started in 1986 by Tank and Hopfield [10], they used the LP circuit in their approach to solving a linear programming problem. By improving their model, Kennedy and Chua [11] introduced another method to solve linear programming problems where the convergence of solutions is guaranteed. This insists most of the researchers (Maa and Shanblat [12], Xia [13], Nguyen [14], Malek and Yari [15], Malek and Alipour [16], Cichocki et al., [17], Effati et al., [18]) to turn their interest in solving linear as well as non-linear optimization problems using neural networks. Effati et al., [1] proposed two fuzzy neural networks for solving two types of fuzzy LP problems which are fuzzy shortest path problem and fuzzy maximum flow problem. Selvaraj and Pandian [19] constructed a crisp neural network to solve fully fuzzy LP problems.

In this work, a new fuzzy energy function is constructed using the fuzzy norm discussed in Effati et al., [1]. Then, we construct a new fuzzy neural network for finding an approximate optimal solution of fuzzy linear programming problems with the fuzzy objective function. The convergence of the proposed fuzzy neural network to the equilibrium point is shown and also, the relation between

equilibrium point of the fuzzy energy function and an optimal solution of the fuzzy shortest path problem is derived. Applicability of the method is shown by the fuzzy shortest path problem.

2. PRELIMINARIES

We need the following definitions and theorems which can be found in Madan M Gupta et al., [20], Effati et al., [1], and Pandian [9].

Definition 2.1: Let X be a classical non-empty set and a set $A \subseteq X$. A fuzzy set \tilde{A} with the membership function $\mu(x)$ is defined as $\tilde{A} = \{ (x, \mu(x)) : x \in X \}$, where $\mu(x)$ is a function from X to $[0,1]$.

Definition 2.2: The α -cut of a fuzzy set \tilde{A} where $\alpha \in [0,1]$ is defined as ${}^\alpha\tilde{A} = \{x : \mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) \geq \alpha, x \in X\}$. It is also denoted by the interval ${}^\alpha\tilde{A} = [A^l, A^r]$, where A^l and A^r are the lower and upper bounds of the closed interval.

Definition 2.3: A fuzzy number $\tilde{a} = (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4)$ is a fuzzy set from the real line \mathbb{R} with the membership function $\mu_{\tilde{a}}(x)$ satisfying the following conditions:

- (i) $\mu_{\tilde{a}}(x)$ is a continuous mapping from \mathbb{R} to the closed interval $[0,1]$.
- (ii) $\mu_{\tilde{a}}(x) = 1$ at $x \in [a_2, a_3]$.
- (iii) $\mu_{\tilde{a}}(x) = 0$ for every $x \in (-\infty, a_1] \cup [a_4, \infty)$.
- (iv) $\mu_{\tilde{a}}(x)$ is strictly decreasing and continuous on $[a_3, a_4]$.
- (v) $\mu_{\tilde{a}}(x)$ is strictly increasing and continuous on $[a_1, a_2]$.

Definition 2.4: Let $\tilde{a} = (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4)$ and $\tilde{b} = (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4)$ be two trapezoidal fuzzy numbers. Then,

- (i) \tilde{a} and \tilde{b} are said to be equal, if $a_i = b_i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$.
- (ii) \tilde{a} is said to be less than or equal \tilde{b} if $a_i \leq b_i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$.
- (iii) \tilde{a} is said to be positive if $a_1 \geq 0$.

Definition 2.5: The α -cut of a trapezoidal fuzzy number $\tilde{a} = (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4)$ is given as ${}^\alpha\tilde{a} = [a_1 + \alpha(a_2 - a_1), a_4 - \alpha(a_4 - a_3)]$ for all $\alpha \in [0,1]$.

Theorem 2.1: (Lyapunov function method) Let x^* be an equilibrium point for the system $\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = f(x(t))$. Let $V : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a continuously differentiable function such that

- (i) $V(x^*) = 0$ and $V(x) > 0, \forall x \neq x^*$.
- (ii) $V(x) \rightarrow \infty$ when $\|x\| \rightarrow \infty$.
- (iii) $\frac{dV(x)}{dt} < 0$ for all $x \neq x^*$.

Then, $x = x^*$ is globally asymptotically stable.

Definition 2.6: Any scalar function $V(x)$ that satisfies all the requirements of the Theorem 2.1. is called a Lyapunov function for the equilibrium state $x = x^*$.

Definition 2.7: Let $\tilde{a} = (\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n)$ be a fuzzy vector that consists of fuzzy numbers. Then the fuzzy norm of \tilde{a} , $\|\tilde{a}\|_f$ is defined as $\|\tilde{a}\|_f = (\|\tilde{a}\|_l, \|\tilde{a}\|_u) = (\|a^l\|, \|a^r\|)$, where $\|\tilde{a}\|_l$ and $\|\tilde{a}\|_u$ are Euclidean norms of the lower and upper values of the fuzzy vector \tilde{a} , $a^l = (a_1^l, a_2^l, \dots, a_n^l)$ and $a^r = (a_1^r, a_2^r, \dots, a_n^r)$ respectively.

Theorem 2.2: Let \tilde{f} be a fuzzy differentiable function of $x \in \Omega \subseteq R$. If x is a point of local minimum, then $\tilde{\nabla}f(x) \approx \tilde{0}$.

3. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

Let $F(R)$ be the set of all triangular or trapezoidal fuzzy numbers. Now, we consider m equality constraints and n decision variables. The mathematical formulation of a linear programming problem with fuzzy objective function as follows:

$$(FP) \text{ Minimize } \sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{c}_j x_j$$

subject to

$$\sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} x_j = b_i, \quad \text{for all } i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

$$x_j \geq 0, \quad \text{for all } j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

where, for all i and j , the variables $a_{ij}, x_j, b_i \in R$, $\tilde{c}_j \in F(R)$. We can define a matrix $A = [a_{ij}]$ as the coefficient matrix of the constraint and a column matrix $b = [b_i]$ as the right-hand side coefficient of the constraint.

3.1 Fuzzy shortest path problem

Consider a directed graph $G = (S, N)$ with n arcs, m nodes, and an arc length \tilde{c}_{ij} is a fuzzy quantity combined with each arc $(i, j) \in N$. Our main aim is to find the shortest path from the source node to the sink node that is, a path of least length from a precise source node to another sink node. The mathematical model of the given FSP problem can be written as a fuzzy LP problem as,

$$(FSP) \text{ Minimize } \tilde{z} = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m \tilde{c}_{ij} x_{ij}$$

subject to

$$\sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij} - \sum_{k=1}^m x_{ki} = \begin{cases} 1 & i = 1 \\ 0 & i = 2, 3, \dots, m-1 \\ -1 & i = m \end{cases}$$

$$x_{ij} \geq 0 \quad \forall i, j$$

where, for all i and j , $x_{ij} \in R$, $\tilde{c}_{ij} \in F(R)$, a set of all fuzzy numbers whose membership functions are linear. Also, we define node-arc incidence matrix as $A, \tilde{c} = (\tilde{c}_{11} \quad \tilde{c}_{12} \quad \dots \quad \tilde{c}_{ij} \quad \dots \quad \tilde{c}_{mm})$ cost matrix and $b = (1 \quad 0 \quad \dots \quad 0 \quad -1)^T$.

4. FUZZY NEURAL NETWORK MODEL

In this section, for solving a linear programming problem with the fuzzy objective function, A new neural network namely, fuzzy neural network based on fuzzy norm introduced by Effati et al. [1] is introduced. A new fuzzy energy function is defined using Lagrange multiplier as follows:

$$\tilde{E}(x, y) = \|\tilde{c}^T x\|_f^2 + \frac{1}{2} y^T \|Ax - b\|^2, \quad x \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

By making the multiplier active into the energy function the network will converge faster. For minimizing the fuzzy energy function stated in (1), the following governing differential equation is obtained in a fuzzy environment using the conjugate gradient learning algorithm

$$\frac{\tilde{d}}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = -\tilde{\nabla} \tilde{E}(x, y), \quad x, y \in R \quad (2)$$

where $\tilde{\nabla} \tilde{E}$ is the gradient of the energy function \tilde{E} in the fuzzy environment and the α -cut of \tilde{E} , ${}^\alpha \tilde{E} = [{}^\alpha \tilde{E}^l, {}^\alpha \tilde{E}^r]$.

Now, $\tilde{\nabla} \tilde{E} = \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{E}}{\partial x_1}, \frac{\partial \tilde{E}}{\partial x_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial \tilde{E}}{\partial x_n} \right)$, where, $\frac{\partial \tilde{E}}{\partial x_i} = \left[\frac{\partial \tilde{E}^l}{\partial x_i}, \frac{\partial \tilde{E}^r}{\partial x_i} \right]$.

From (2), the following dynamic system of fuzzy differential equations is obtained.

$$\frac{\tilde{d}}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{c}^T (\tilde{c}x) + y^T A^T (Ax - b) \\ \frac{\|Ax - b\|^2}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

For computing purposes, the above fuzzy network can be represented by the following dynamic system using the α -cuts. Since the decision variables are crisp it is enough to consider only lower values of the α -cuts.

$$\frac{d^l}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} (c^l)^T (c^l x) + y^T A^T (Ax - b) \\ \frac{\|Ax - b\|^2}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

By solving the system (4) for all the values of α in $[0,1]$, we obtain minima for the fuzzy energy function $\tilde{E}(x, y)$.

Now, we prove the stability of the proposed fuzzy neural network (4) which is used to solve the problem (FP).

Theorem 4.1: The fuzzy energy function $\tilde{E}(x, y)$ is a Lyapunov function for the fuzzy neural network (4).

Proof: Now, for every (x, y) , $\tilde{E}(x, y)$ is always a positive fuzzy number.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } \frac{d^r}{dt} (\tilde{E}(x, y)) &= ((c^r)^T (c^r x) + y^T A^T (Ax - b)) \frac{d^r x}{dt} + \frac{\|Ax - b\|^2}{2} \frac{d^r y}{dt} \\ &= - \left(\frac{d^r x}{dt} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{d^r y}{dt} \right)^2 < 0. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\frac{d^l}{dt} \tilde{E}(x, y) \leq \frac{d^r}{dt} \tilde{E}(x, y)$, That is, $\frac{\tilde{d}}{dt} \tilde{E}(x, y) < \tilde{0}$. This shows that the proposed fuzzy neural network (4) is globally asymptotically stable. Therefore, the function $\tilde{E}(x, y)$ is a Lyapunov function for the system (4).

Hence the theorem is proved.

Now, we shall establish a relation between the equilibrium point of the fuzzy neural network (4) or the minima for the fuzzy energy function $\tilde{E}(x, y)$ and the optimal solution of the linear programming problem with fuzzy objective function (FP).

Theorem 4.2: If the linear programming problem with fuzzy objective function (FP) has an optimal solution and (x^*, y^*) is the equilibrium point for the fuzzy neural networks (4) then x^* will be the optimal solution for the problem (FP).

Proof: Now, since x^* is the equilibrium point for the fuzzy neural networks (4).

we have $\tilde{\nabla} \tilde{E}(x^*, y^*) \approx \tilde{0}$ and (x^*, y^*) is a feasible solution to the problem (FP).

From the energy function (1) and since \tilde{x}^* is a feasible solution to the problem (FP), we have $\tilde{E}(x^*, y^*) \approx \tilde{c}^T x^*$.

Since $\tilde{E}(x^*, y^*)$ is minimum for the network (4), the problem (FP) attains its minimum at (x^*, y^*) .

Hence, the theorem is proved.

Remark 4.1: From the above theorem, we can assure that the proposed fuzzy neural network (4) will converge to the optimum solution of the problem (FP) if it exists.

5. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

In this section, the proposed method is illustrated with the help of a fuzzy shortest path problem which can be transformed as a linear programming problem with fuzzy objective function:

Example 1: consider an FSP problem shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Fuzzy Shortest Path Problem

Now, Mathematical model of the fuzzy shortest path problem (Figure 1) is represented as a fuzzy LP model which is given below:

Minimize
$$\tilde{z} = (4, 7, 7)x_{12} + (1, 2, 4)x_{13} + (2, 2, 5)x_{14} + (3, 3, 4)x_{25} + (2, 3, 4)x_{35} + (4, 5, 6)x_{36} + (6, 8, 9)x_{46} + (4, 6, 7)x_{57} + (6, 7, 9)x_{67}$$
 subject to :

$$\sum_{j=1}^7 x_{ij} - \sum_{k=1}^7 x_{ki} = \begin{cases} 1 & i=1 \\ 0 & i=2,3,\dots,6 \\ -1 & i=7 \end{cases}$$

$$x_{ij} \geq 0 \text{ for all } i, j$$

The following left values are obtained through our proposed network for each $\alpha \in [0,1]$. These values become our required solution to the given problem.

From Table 1, it can be concluded (by rounding off) that the solution to the given problem is $x_{12} = x_{14} = x_{25} = x_{36} = x_{46} = x_{67} = 0$ and $x_{13} = x_{35} = x_{57} = 1$, the required shortest path is (1) \rightarrow (3) \rightarrow (5) \rightarrow (7) and required minimum distance is (7, 11, 15).

α	x'_{12}	x'_{13}	x'_{14}	x'_{25}	x'_{35}	x'_{36}	x'_{46}	x'_{57}	x'_{67}
0	0	.998	.001	0	.997	0	0	.997	0
0.1	0	.997	.001	0	.996	0	0	.996	0
0.2	0	.997	.001	0	.996	0	0	.996	0
0.3	0	.997	.001	0	.995	0	0	.996	0
0.4	0	.996	.001	0	.995	0	0	.995	0
0.5	0	.996	.001	0	.994	0	0	.995	0
0.6	0	.995	.001	0	.994	0	0	.994	0
0.7	0	.995	.002	0	.993	0	0	.994	0
0.8	0	.994	.002	0	.992	0	0	.993	0
0.9	0	.994	.002	0	.992	0	0	.993	0
1	0	.993	.002	0	.991	0	0	.992	0

Table 1 Solution for FSP problem at each alpha level

Now, the following figures Figure 2 and Figure 3 shows that the convergence of all decision variables in the network at $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ respectively.

Figure 2: Network behaviour for Eg.1 at alpha=0

Figure 3: Network behaviour for Eg.1 at alpha=1

Remark 5.1: The optimum solution got by the proposed fuzzy network (4) for Example 1. is same and gets faster convergence as the optimum obtained in Effati et al. [1].

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a linear programming problem where the fuzzy coefficient involves only in the objective function is solved. Constructed a new fuzzy function using a fuzzy norm which was introduced and dealt with Effati [1] by making the Lagrange multiplier dynamic with each iteration the proposed network works faster. The relation between the energy function and the optimal solution to the problem is proved. The stability of the proposed method is proved using the Lyapunov function method and the efficiency of the method is illustrated through a sample fuzzy shortest path problem.

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